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P. S. Aithal
Srinivas Institute of
Management Studies,
Pandeshwar, Mangalore,
India

How an effective leadership and governance supports to achieve institutional vision, mission and objectives

P. S. Aithal

Abstract

Effective leadership by setting values and participative decision-making process is key not only to achieve the vision, mission and goals of the institution but also in building the organizational culture. The formal and informal arrangements in the institution to co-ordinate the academic and administrative planning and implementation reflects the institutions efforts in achieving its vision. This paper focus on the vision, mission and the objectives identified for a higher education institution and needs to be addressed through its distinctive characteristics by considering Srinivas Institute of Management Studies as an example. The role of top management, principal and faculty in design and implementation of its quality policy and plans both in Teaching and Services are identified. The involvement of the leadership in ensuring the policy statements and action plans for fulfillment of the stated mission, formulation of action plans for all operations and incorporation of the same into the institutional strategic plan, Interaction with stakeholders, Proper support for policy and planning through need analysis, research inputs and consultations with the stakeholders, Reinforcing the culture of excellence, and Champion organizational change. The various procedures adopted by the institution to monitor and evaluate policies and plans of the institution for effective implementation and improvement from time to time are discussed. Details of the academic leadership provided to the faculty by the top management, the college strategy to groom leadership at various levels, How does the college delegate authority and provide operational autonomy to the departments / units of the institution and work towards decentralized governance system, and the strategy of college to promote a culture of participative management are elaborated.

Keywords: Effective leadership, Governance in Higher education, Efficiency in higher education institutions

1. Introduction

Effective leadership by setting values and participative decision-making process is key not only to achieve the vision, mission and goals of the institution but also in building the organizational culture. The formal and informal arrangements in the institution to co-ordinate the academic and administrative planning and implementation reflects the institutions efforts in achieving its vision. The vision statement is the institution's destination for the length of the strategic plan. Vision statements contain the specific characteristics or features that will define the organization in its future state. The vision statement is used to motivate and inspire, and is understood to be achievable. The mission statement is simply a purpose statement. It explains in one or two sentences what the institution seeks to accomplish, why it exists, and what ultimate result should be expected. Language in the mission statement is usually expressed using verbs in the infinitive (to increase, to improve, etc.) and also should identify any problems or conditions that will be changed. Gap Analysis is a procedure to assesses the "gap" between the institution's current status and the specific features of the vision. It also identifies what actions need to be taken to close the gap and can be studied through SWOT Analysis. SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) is used as a framework for the environmental scan. The procedure allows planners to support the gap analysis with additional information about what actions need to be taken in the strategic plan to move the institution to its vision [1-2].

Information collected through the environmental scan is general in nature and provides the organization's planners with a common understanding of trends and issues for the future so they are able to develop a vision. The environmental scan provides the basis for organization-wide discussions focused on "futuring". A good environmental scan does not attempt to develop detailed data or market analysis, and does not use projections based on current trends, unless those trends are seen to be evolving into a larger issue. The scan is used to inform the

Correspondence:
P. S. Aithal
Srinivas Institute of
Management Studies,
Pandeshwar, Mangalore,
India

organization’s vision and identify the broad strategic objectives that will become a guideline for an action plan. There are two major components to an environmental scan, the external environment and the internal environment. Both should be examined to determine whether or not members of the organization have a unified view of the future and what resources they believe they have or will need as they move forward [3-5].

This paper focus on the vision, mission and the objectives identified for a higher education institution and needs to be addressed through its distinctive characteristics by considering Srinivas Institute of Management Studies (SIMS) as an example. The role of top management, principal and faculty in design and implementation of its quality policy and plans both in Teaching and Services are identified. The involvement of the leadership in ensuring the policy statements and action plans for fulfillment of the stated mission, formulation of action plans for all operations and incorporation of the same into the institutional strategic plan, Interaction with stakeholders, Proper support for policy and planning through need analysis, research inputs and consultations with the stakeholders, Reinforcing the culture of excellence, and Champion organizational change. The various procedures adopted by the institution to monitor and evaluate policies and plans of the institution for effective implementation and improvement from time to time are discussed. Details of the academic leadership provided to the faculty by the top management, the college strategy to groom leadership at various levels, How does the college delegate authority and provide operational autonomy to the departments / units of the institution and work towards decentralized governance system, and the strategy of college to promote a culture of participative management are elaborated [6].

2. Quality Based on Vision & Mission

Drishti - The Vision:

Extension of opportunity to all aspirants for education, and expansion across all realms of knowledge, upholding values of equality and service to mankind.

Chatushpatha - The Mission:

Our mission is to nurture a new generation of youth through providing quality education and skills matching the requirement of a harmonious, self-reliant and developed society and values inclined to serve with selfless devotion in whatever capacity they assume and wherever they work. This also aims to inculcate values of human dignity and mutual respect, generate the spirit of enquiry, induce healthy competitions, encourage sustainable accomplishments and ensure enriching rewards.

Objectives:

- To make available world class education with an Indian ethos to the student community
- To create centre of excellence imparting quality education.
- To offer to the society /industry, academically empowered and ready for the job professionals in diverse fields.
- To foster research and dissipate research findings for the all round development of the nation and community at large.
- To contribute to nation building by generating a pool of human resources trained in science, technology, humanities, management, education and research.
- To maintain dynamic equilibrium between the various educational institutions and the economic, socio-cultural and ecological environment.

Distinctive characteristics of Vision and Mission:

The distinctive characteristics of vision & mission are given in table 1.

Table 1: Institutions distinctive characteristics and needs addressed.

S. No.	Institutions Distinctive Characteristics	Needs Addressed
1	Enhancing educational opportunities	Creating equality of opportunity to all aspirants to prepare their future through education and to build a generation to serve with selfless devotion in whatever capacity they assume and wherever they work.
2	Offering diverse courses	Education that suits the interest and talent of the students for contributing professionals in all walks of life which will reflect human dignity, mutual respect and induce healthy competition.
3	Maintaining quality	To obtaining world class education in an atmosphere of freedom and secularism so that the institution becomes centre of excellence.
4	Increasing employability	Academically empowered and ready for the job professionals in diverse fields resulting in a self reliance society leading to enriching rewards.
5	Solving community based problems	To foster spirit of research among the young professionals so as to solve community problems for the all-round development of the nation and community at large.
6	Creating pool of human resources	To maintain productively engaged youth trained in science, technology, humanities and management which will contribute nation building.
7	Promoting inter institutional collaborations	Obtaining quality education with Indian ethos, contributing dynamic equilibrium between various institutions and expansion across all realms of knowledge.
8	Maintaining harmony with environment	To encourage sustainable accomplishment for a harmonious self reliance society maintaining dynamic equilibrium between economic, socio-cultural and ecological environment.

3. Role of Management in Design & Implementation of Quality Policy

The role of top management, Principal and Faculty in design and implementation of its quality policy and plans both in Teaching and Services are given in tables 2 -3.

3.1. Quality Teaching:

Table 2: Quality policy at various levels and plan of implementation

S. No.	Level	Quality Policy	Plan of Implementation
1	Top Management	Maintain high standards in imparting education.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Setting objectives relevant to policy. 2. Hiring quality professional to fill faculty positions. 3. Reward competitively. 4. Ensure minimum attrition.
2	Principal	Motivate and monitor a team of competent faculty.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. (a) Setting up rules & regulations of the institution (b) Identifying and hiring (c) Induction (d) Performance management 2. Evolve a salary structure suited to the industry 3. (a) Generate higher job satisfaction through incentives. (b) Faculty Development programs (c) Participatory Decision making (d) Transparency in Administration (e) Collective responsibility 4. (a) Team building, (b) Faculty Development programs (c) Participatory Decision making (d) Transparency in Administration (e) Collective responsibility
3	Faculty	Absorb the spirit of institutional values and maintain efficiency	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Maintain uninterrupted work schedules. 2. Impart quality education. 3. Try out various techniques in pedagogy. 4. Examinations & fair assessment in time 5. Maintaining satisfactory student interest.

3.2. Quality Services:

Table 3: Quality services at various levels and plan of implementation

S. No.	Level	Quality Services	Plan of Implementation
1	Top Management	Provision of infrastructure and facilities suitable for effective services.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provide appropriate building, equipments, etc. 2. To encourage utilization of the facilities to optimum levels. 3. Cater to further requirements as per needs.
2	Principal	1. Ensure availability maintenance of improved infrastructure and services.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Prepare inventory of infrastructure requirement. 2. Ensure availability of the required resources. 3. Utilization of resources optimally. 4. Evolve better man management practices. 5. Introduce both conventional and innovative tools for operationalizing services. 6. Training & Development.
3	Faculty	To integrate individual interest and institutional interest in offering services.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Adherence to regulations and fulfillment of requirement. 2. Developing a suitable pedagogy. 3. Utilization of library as a Knowledge resource. 4. Self-development through continuing education. 5. Provide support services to maintain core services.

4. Roll of the Leadership in Ensuring Institutions Policy
4.1 The policy statements and action plans for fulfillment of the stated mission:

The leadership of the institution involves in preparation and implementation of policy statements and action plans for fulfillment of its stated mission.

4.2 Formulation of action plans:

Table 4: Action plan and institutional strategic plan at various operational processes

S. No.	Operational Processes	Action plan	Institutional strategic plan
1	Admission	Ensuring full admission	Maintaining equality of opportunity through religious and linguistic groups
2	Education - teaching & curriculum	Ensuring Quality education	Effective teaching-learning processes, adding to innovations and best practices
3	Placement	Ensuring job opportunity for everybody	Introducing Skill building and certification programmes
4	Personality Development	Providing co-curricular and extra-curricular activities	Value addition
5	Administration of services	Effective support services	Adoption of time saving and error free newer technology in office automation
6	Social responsibility	Involving students in social activities	Operationalization of institutes own service based NGO-SIRRA

4.3 Interaction with stakeholders:

The institute maintains interaction with all its stakeholders in the following ways (Table 5):

Table 5: Interaction with stakeholders

S. No.	Stake holders	Ensuring Involvement
1	Management	Continuous feedback and consultation
2	Parents	Regular meetings and contact
3	Students	Classes and activities
4	Alumni	Meetings & Suggestions
5	University	Responding to requirement
6	Industry	Placement and projects
7	Government	Compliance to regulations
8	Community	Public relations

4.4 Proper support for policy and planning through need analysis, research inputs and consultations with the stakeholders:

- (i) The institutional leadership encourages the faculty through proper support by developing suitable policy to address the need analysis of students such as obtaining admission, attending classes, following curriculum, writing the examination, securing the high marks, preparing for competition, surviving challenges, obtaining placement and prospering in career.
- (ii) The institutional leadership encourages the faculty through proper support by developing suitable policy to address the problems of the community through undertaking research activities and inputs and come out with solutions which best solve the problems in the areas of commerce, information technology, management and social work.
- (iii) The institutional leadership encourages the faculty through proper support by developing suitable policy to address the problems of the industry through understanding the emerging requirements in the job market, changes in the curriculum, as well as offering consultancy services.

4.5 Reinforcing the culture of excellence:

The institutional leadership involves in reinforcing the culture of excellence through creating spiritual forums, literary forums, yoga and mind control programmes, trainings and personality development programmes, academic pursuit through research centers and re-enforcing discipline.

4.6 Champion organizational change:

The institutional leadership involves in organizational change by incorporating departmentalization, decentralization, knowledge sharing, technology development, infrastructure development, admission process, and academic leadership.

4.7 Procedures adopted by the institution to monitor and evaluate policies and plans of the institution for effective implementation and improvement from time to time:

The following procedures are adopted to monitor and evaluate policies and plans of the institute:

(a) Students:

The policy of the institution is to transform the students into useful, employable and productive citizens through providing quality education and skills. The college offers a verity of courses to suites the need and interest of the students and provide quick employment. In all courses qualified, trained and experienced faculty provide education, conduct examination, evaluate and assess the potential of the students and encourages them for their continued growth. Over and

above this, many certification programs are offered to the students to further bridge the gap between curriculum and industry.

(b) Teaching Faculty:

The policy of the institution is to identify, attract, motivate and maintain a team of quality professionals who would play a key role in building high caliber students. In order to attain this, the institution ensures that its personnel are appropriately identified, compensated, and retained. The faculty members are oriented with necessary responsibility and accountability to carry out their task successfully. The faculties are also trained to enhance the teaching ability evaluated through appraisal and feedback from the students.

(c) Non-Teaching Faculty: The supporting staff of the institution are focused on the strengthening their services and greater satisfaction to the teaching faculty and the students. In order to attain this they are trained in use of computers, effective office management skills, the same will be evaluated through regular interaction with the staff and taking self-appraisal reports and feedback from the Office Manager.

(d) Organizational:

The institution for its own is committed to maintain high standards in imparting education contributing to principles of secularism, diversity, inclusion and integration. The institution maintains a rich mix of faculty and students of all religious, linguistic and cultural group. Students of all parts of the country are enrolled and the courses offered provides a wide range of career options. While at the same time teaching and learning form the main thrust of the institution, all round development of the students is given due importance through promoting, co-curricular, extracurricular, social service and research programs.

The academic leadership provided to the faculty by the top management are:

(1) Set standards:

The faculty are allowed to establish desired levels of knowledge and prepare the students accordingly.

- (a) Teaching: Faculty uses varied and appropriate methods as per the choice of the situation
- (b) Assessment: Faculty conducts periodic assessment through internal examinations, assignments, presentations and seminars.
- (d) Attendance: Faculty maintains the attendance of each students on regular basis and ensure that the students maintains minimum required level of attendance through reducing absence, late comings and drop-outs.
- (e) Inspiring through providing himself as an example: Faculty strives to maintain a high profile so as to become role models for the students.

(2) Measuring performance:

- (a) Periodic examinations: The performance of the students is evaluated through periodic internal examinations.
- (b) Involving in activities: Students are involved in all activities which promote their growth and development.
- (c) Feedback based improvement: Students are given feedback on their performance and motivated to improve.

(3) Enforcing discipline:

- (a) Preparing guidelines: The faculty prepare guidelines on the dos and don'ts inside and outside the class rooms following the regulations provided in the college colander.
- (b) Enforcing control: Late coming, disobedience, bad habits etc. are discouraged.
- (c) Monitoring: The faculty actively participate in the disciplinary committee as well as providing counseling services.

(4) Imbibing values:

The values of the institution as reflected in the vision and mission of the institution are translated into action through imbibing values among the students.

(5) Character formation:

The faculty works closely with the students to influence their character formation such as gender sensitivity, religious

tolerance, linguistic and geographical integration and moral integrity.

(6) Personality building:

Skill development programmes are offered in addition to regular classes which would build their capacity for communication, language comprehension, self-esteem, emotional intelligence, dignity, and appeal.

5. Institutional Strategy to Groom Leadership

The institution grooms leadership at students and Faculty levels as shown in following tables:

(i) For Students:

The various ways of grooming the leadership at student level is given in table 6.

Table 6: Grooming the leadership at student level

S. No.	Levels of leadership	Ways of grooming leadership
1	Academic leadership	1. Teaching oriented to catering the needs of the high achievers. 2. Time bound assignments & Presentations with strict adherence to quality. 3. Use of Library & Technology as learning resource. 4. Exposure to industry. 5. Interaction with experts and visiting faculty. 6. Participation & presentation in conference, seminars and workshops. 7. Periodic internal assessment and examinations.
2	Program organizing leadership	1. Formulating programmes which suit requirements of growth. 2. Articulating roles and responsibilities. 2. Participatory decision making and 3. Involving in implementation. 4. Working in teams 5. Sharing, collaborating and contributing 6. Accepting feedback and improvements. 7. Corrective actions & learning.
3	Sports & Games leadership	1. Developing sportsman spirit. 2. Encouraging participation. 3. Coaching 4. Learning to accept failures. 5. Reviving ambitions 6. Mustering courage. 7. Winning for team and establishing fame.
4	Cultural activities leadership	1. Identifying talents 2. Practicing trails 3. Organising events 4. Promoting participation 5. Extending appreciation 6. Rewarding 7. Developing quest for perfection.

(ii) For Faculty Members:

The various ways of grooming the leadership at faculty level is given in table 7.

Table 7: Grooming the leadership at Faculty level

S. No.	Levels of leadership	Ways of grooming leadership
1	Career	1. Providing adequate opportunity 2. Entrusting responsibility 3. Creating confidence 4. Building skills 5. Upgrading knowledge 6. Encouraging research activities 7. Attaining job satisfaction 8. Excelling in career

The following six values with corresponding practices are embedded in the Institute's culture developing the full potential of its faculty members and students.

(1) Self Responsibility: Individual takes responsibility of their job, team, function, Institution, the way they wish it to be.

(2) Authentic Communication: Individual communication is open, honest, transparent and vulnerable.

(3) Trust: Individuals feel safe enough to try out new behaviors and take risks without fear.

(4) Personal and group process skills: Individual and the Institution have established protocol's and developed skills which are regularly deployed to resolve interpersonal issues that come across & are resolved quickly and clearly.

(5) Learning and Growing: Individuals are encouraged and rewarded to work on the real growth issues necessary for professional and personal development within the framework of the organization. Individuals are ever challenging themselves and supporting each other to develop and grow.

(6) Caring: The organizational leadership demonstrate in tangible ways concern for individual employee well being. Employees feel valued and are inspired to put in their best effort.

The college delegate authority and provide operational autonomy to the departments of the institution and work towards decentralized governance system (Table 8).

Table 8: Departments of the institution and work towards decentralized governance system

S. No.	Department	Delegating authority and Operational Autonomy
1	Business Management	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The department has a course co-ordinator who receives instruction from the head of the institution and reports. 2. There are separate Course-coordinators for UG and PG programs. 3. Faculty has opportunity to choose the subject to be taught in each semester every year 4. Faculty in-charge of the subject prepares the teaching plan corresponding to the paper. 5. For each specialization, there is a faculty co-ordinator. 6. Planning teaching-learning tools such as preparation of Time-table and allocation of papers are done in consultation with individual faculty. 7. Teachers are in-charge of forum activities of students. 8. Class teachers are designated for all classes. 9. There are student co-coordinators for each specialization. 10. Preparation of academic calendar based on time frame set by the University for planning and organizing of activities is done by Course co-ordinators. 11. Planning industrial visits, forum activities, Guest lectures, and initiation of project proposals are done by course co-ordinators in consultation with specialization co-ordinaors. 12. Staff meetings are conducted by course co-ordinators regularly. 13. Each faculty express his views in staff meetings. 14. Forecasting annual events which contribute to student development is done by Head of the institution together with course co-ordinators. 15. Matters such as conducting internal exams are decided collectively in staff meetings. 16. Faculty makes independent assessment of student performance. 17. Student have freedom to give feedback and suggestion on faculty.
2	Computer Science	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The department has a course co-ordinator who receives instruction from the head of the institution and reports. 2. There are separate Course-coordinators for UG and PG programs. 3. Faculty has opportunity to choose the subject to be taught in each semester every year 4. Faculty in-charge of the subject prepares the teaching plan corresponding to the paper. 5. For each specialization, there is a faculty co-ordinator. 6. Planning teaching-learning tools such as preparation of Time-table and allocation of papers are done in consultation with individual faculty. 7. Teachers are in-charge of forum activities of students. 8. Class teachers are designated for all classes. 9. There are student co-coordinators for each specialization. 10. Preparation of academic calendar based on time frame set by the University for planning and organizing of activities is done by Course co-ordinators. 11. Planning industrial visits, forum activities, Guest lectures, and initiation of project proposals are done by course co-ordinators in consultation with specialization co-ordinaors. 12. Staff meetings are conducted by course co-ordinators regularly. 13. Each faculty express his views in staff meetings. 14. Forecasting annual events which contribute to student development is done by Head of the institution together with course co-ordinators.. 15. Matters such as conducting internal exams are decided collectively in staff meetings. 16. Faculty makes independent assessment of student performance. 17. Student have freedom to give feedback and suggestion on faculty. 18. Industrial visits, group projects, consultations with IT & ITES organizations and initiation of project proposals are planned in the faculty meetings.
3	Social Work	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The department has a course co-ordinator who receives instruction from the head of the institution and reports. 2. Faculty are involved in choosing the subject to be taught in each semester. 3. Faculty in-charge of the subject prepares the teaching plan corresponding to the paper. 4. For each specialization, there is a faculty co-ordinator. 5. Planning teaching-learning tools such as preparation of Time-table and allocation of papers are done in consultation with individual faculty. 6. Teachers are in-charge of forum activities of students.

		<p>7. Class teachers are designated for all classes. 8. There are student co-coordinators for each specialization. 9. Preparation of academic calendar based on time frame set by the University for planning and organizing of activities is done by Course co-ordinators. 10. Planning industrial visits, forum activities, Guest lectures, and initiation of project proposals are done by course co-ordinators in consultation with specialization co-ordinators. 11. Staff meetings are conducted by course co-ordinator regularly. 12. Faculty can express views in staff meetings. 13. Decisions are taken together. 14. Forecasting annual events which contribute to student development is done by Head of the institution together with course co-ordinator. 15. Matters such as conducting internal exams are decided collectively in staff meetings. 16. Faculty makes independent assessment of student performance. 17. Student have freedom to give feedback and suggestion on faculty. 18. Industrial visits, and community based social service activities are planned together with student representatives. 19. Outdoor programmes like camps, campaign, and surveys are planned in faculty meetings. 20. Students are encouraged to make independent choice of research projects.</p>
4	Commerce	<p>1. The department has a course co-ordinator who receives instruction from the head of the institution and reports. 2. Faculty has opportunity to choose the subject to be taught in each semester every year 3. Faculty in-charge of the subject prepares the teaching plan corresponding to the paper. 4. Planning teaching-learning tools such as preparation of Time-table and allocation of papers are done in consultation with individual faculty. 5. Teachers are in-charge of forum activities of students. 6. Class teachers are designated for all classes. 7. There are student co-coordinators for each specialization. 8. Preparation of academic calendar based on time frame set by the University for planning and organizing of activities is done by Course co-ordinators. 9. Planning industrial visits, forum activities, Guest lectures, and initiation of project proposals are done by course co-ordinators in consultation with specialization co-ordinators. 10. Staff meetings are conducted by course co-ordinator regularly. 11. Each faculty express his views in staff meetings. 12. Forecasting annual events which contribute to student development is done by Head of the institution together with course co-ordinator. 13. Matters such as conducting internal exams are decided collectively in staff meetings. 14. Faculty makes independent assessment of student performance. 15. Student have freedom to give feedback and suggestion on faculty.</p>

The institute promotes a culture of participative management by involving the staff and students in various activities. All decisions of the institution are governed by management of facts, information and objectives. Both students and faculties allowed to express themselves of any suggestions to improve the excellence in any aspect of the Institute.

Strategic Level

- The principal, course co-ordinators and staff members are involved in defining the policies and procedures, framing guidelines and rules & regulations pertaining to admission, placement, discipline, grievance, counseling, training & development, and library services etc., and effectively implementing the same to ensure smooth and systematic functioning of the institute.
- For the various programs to be conducted by the institute all the staff members will meet, discuss, share their opinion and plan for the event and form various committees involving students and coordinate with others.
- Staff members are also involved in deciding academic activities and examinations to be conducted by the college.

Functional Level

- For the various events to be conducted by the department, all the staff members will meet, discuss, share their opinion and plan for the event and form various committees involving students and coordinate with others.

- Teaching Staff of various departments participate in sharing the knowledge by discussing on the latest trends in their respective area of specialization.
- The co-ordinators and the members of different departments meet together and plan the programmes to be conducted.

Operational level

- All the staff members are involved in deciding day to day academic activities of the department.
- Students support to maintain the discipline to ensure smooth and systematic functioning of the institute.
- Office staff are involved in executing day to day support services for both students and faculties.

6. Conclusion

1. The vision, mission and goals of the institution are in tune with the objectives of higher education.
2. The governance of the institution is reflective of an effective leadership.
3. The institution practices decentralization and participative management.
4. The institution formulates its strategic planning and interacts with stakeholders.
5. The institution monitors and evaluates its policies and plans.
6. The institution grooms leadership at various levels.
7. All decisions of the institution are governed by management of facts, information and objectives.

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